

ASHURALI ZOKHIRY'S ARTICLE "WHEN WILL IT BE?" AS A HISTORICAL SOURCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7915106>

Abstract. *In the article brief life of Ashurali Zahiri, one of the national intellectuals of the Fergana Valley, and his new views on the problems that arose in the public life of Turkestan in the late 19th - early 20th centuries illuminated in his article "When will it be".*

Keywords: *jadidism, Ashurali Zahiri, Turkestan, darkness, ignorance, illiteracy, education, enlightenment, book, "usuli savtiya", renewal, science, development.*

INTRODUCTION

Ashurali Zahiri (1885-1937) was one of the jadid enlighteners who at the beginning of the 20th century worked within his profession to renew the life of society and rebuild it based on the requirements of the times and spared no effort in this regard, standing alongside prominent figures of the Jadidist movement, progressives, set themselves the goal of reforming human consciousness and thinking through the development of science and education, and bringing colonial Turkestan into the ranks of the developed countries of the world through reforms.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Ashurali Zahiri is a well-known jadid scholar, enlightener, linguist, journalist, translator, lexicographer and scholar of literature. One of the national intellectuals of Fergana Valley, a prominent representative of the Jadidist movement. He was born in 1885 in the village of Oyim near the city of Kokand. Like all people of his time, he received his primary education in an old school. In 1897-1914, he studied at the Madrasah of Muhammad Alikhan (i.e. Madalikhan) in Kokand. During his studies at the madrasah, along with religious knowledge, he deeply studied history, language, and literature, including Arabic, Persian, Azerbaijani, Turkish, Tatar, and Russian languages, as well as Persian-Tajik classical literature. Ashurali Zahiri, who acquired all-round knowledge, taught language and literature at the Russian Tuzem school, as well as at the Jadid school between 1907 (from March 9) and 1917. He teaches as a teacher in courses and schools for the elimination of illiteracy, at Kokand Pedagogical Institute, encourages people to learn languages and be knowledgeable. In 1908-1913, Ashurali Zahiri opened a new school of Darulmu'allimin in the city of Kokand, here he teaches on the basis of "usuli savtiya" and engages in spiritual and educational upbringing. He used examples of classic Uzbek and Eastern literature during his teaching. He also worked at Fergana Pedagogical Technical College, headed by Qori Niazi in Fergana. Here Ashurali Zahiri works together with pedagogues such as Bulat Soliev, Hodi Fayzi, Qori Niazi. His teaching career continued until 1919.

RESEARCH RESULTS

During his career, Ashurali Zahiri tried to show the social situation among the population and their certain strata with his modern views through a series of articles he wrote. Another article of the author, published on May 23, 1914, in "Sadoyi Ferghana" newspaper, is an article called "When will it be?". In the article, the author admitted that the people of Turkestan were unaware of world development and worldly news, and tried to reveal the attitude of the people of Turkestan

to science, books, development and progress. Therefore, he spoke about the level of acceptance of development in the Islamic world at such a time, that it is like collecting millions of books in all fields of science, putting one of our people in this library and when they tell us to acquire some knowledge by reading the books in this library, in order them to increase our rank and status, and if we don't study, they will fill our bellies with food only enough for now, but we careless servants have been lazy and have not use it, we could not use it. In any case, we were satisfied with what we had. We are going this way for a long time - he writes with a laugh. With this, the author criticizes the fact that Muslim countries are lagging behind other countries in terms of development, and instead of developing science and benefiting from it, they are busy feeding themselves and making ends meet.

Why did the author express such opinions? Because, in his opinion, if a Muslim is needed for the work of his time, including office work, or if a person is looking for a teacher for the Sawtiya school, schools like Rashidi, Avloni, which are opened due to the permission of the state, if a person is given permission to publish a newspaper and if an editor is needed, if an accountant is needed for property loans that are being opened everywhere, if a candidate is asked to participate in the State Duma of All-Russia Muslims, in the Petersburg Council, he admits that even if he searches for ten years with the light during the day, he will not find a suitable person. The author concludes that it is known from such cases that we are not aware of modern science and culture. Even if we were not aware, life had to compel. But when faced with various hardships, we have stopped and left the roads that we used to pass with pleasure to the extent that our eyes are not afraid of them, and our minds are not enough. We haven't moved further or since, we have been moving for a long time, but it seems that a lot of time will have to pass before moving forward. But when will it be!, - exclaims the author. Addressing his compatriots with this article, the representative of Jadid, who can benefit his country, nation, identity, family, and himself, when will the experts in all fields come out, when will the nation, the country, and science develop and achieve progress. It raises questions about when Muslim people will achieve a comfortable standard of living. And in this regard, it shows that a number of reforms should be carried out in the country.

Although hundreds of years have passed, our people are still experiencing the processes of development and renewal in social life in our country. This article, which was brought to the attention of our nation so long ago, has not lost its importance as a historical source and has not been included in the scope of special research. That is why we converted it from the old Uzbek script to the current script, prepared it for publication and are bringing it to the attention of researchers.

When will it be?

If we look at the paths that have passed since the beginning of time, the human child is improving and developing in every way day by day and year by year.

In the free world of Haq, every person is finding the feelings created for each individual, even if it is obediently, and he is producing many famous and favorable signs and habits. We don't know what will be invented in a few more years? What do you accept? But this will not be a progressive and perfect mansukh (fortunate person V.K.) and all the creations (acceptable) that have been discovered by the servants in the divine treasure of Haq will not be finished until the world of crisis.

Nowadays, we, the Islamic world, are like that, if we direct a person to the library with millions of all kinds of subjects and give him "As samiy al" book telling 'this library is yours, if you want any kind of book, you can find it and use it if you want. Even if you don't want to use it, try it. But if you gain knowledge using these books, we will increase your rank and status accordingly. Otherwise, we will give your time at the level of laymut (in the meaning of providing food at a sufficient level, V.K). In this world of life like a person who has been brought to the door of paradisiacal pleasure, even if Haq has created a permanent treasure with "no" deficiency to go to its dark lands, or to go to his presence and has sent to us Holly Quran, jame albar va albaxri (sea of goodness, V.K.), that will be a blessing for all our deeds, we, lazy servant, could not and did not think of using it (Islamic world). In any case, we have been satisfied with anything on the level of sufficient. In this way, we are going for indefinite numbers of times.

That's why, if you need one person for one of the jobs of the present time (that is, if you need a Muslim to occupy such a place), e.i. for a school of usuli savtiya, or Rashidi, Avloni schools which are being built with the official permission. If teachers are wanted, or if they want to publish a newspaper or magazine, and need an editor to the editorial board. Perhaps, these days, if the small credit institutions that are opening everywhere need an accountant (учетевод), or if they are called to send a deputation to the meeting of the Council in Petersburg, which is authorized by the internal control of the affairs of the All-Russian Muslims, or if they are elected to the Gosudarstvenny Duma by the decree of our tsar, if you need a decent breed, you won't be able to find him even if you search for ten years with a light during the day.

But if you want to be an imam and a muezzin in a local mosque, or if you want to place a candle on top of someone's grave, or if you need a person to do something like that, you don't have to search for a new one!: it causes quarrels and arguments between several people sending letters and sayings to occupy that place saying 'I will, I have been'. However, it is doubtful that you will earn one hundred soums per year.

It is clear from these cases that we are not aware of modern science and culture. Even if we didn't want to be aware, life had to force us. But what is the happiness and bliss that we do not see with our eyes even if we face various hardships in life? in what? We have become so stubborn that our minds are not enough. We haven't been able to move forward or since, we have been and continue to be, but it seems that a lot of time has to pass before we can move forward. But when will it be?

DISCUSSION

There are more than 25 articles of Ashurali Zahiri, a prominent representative of Turkestan jadidists, which serve to illuminate the country's social, political, spiritual, educational, linguistic, historical, and scientific fields. We did not dwell on his other articles, as the research focused on his article "When will it be?". His articles can be found in "Gazette of the Turkestan Region", "Sadoyi Fergana" and other newspapers of the same period.

CONCLUSION

Ashurali Zahiri, a Jadid luminary who was born in the city of Kokand of Fergana Valley and was active in science, education, upbringing, spirituality and enlightenment, served as an active member of the Jadid activities that took place in the social life of Turkestan at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries, will remain forever in history and in the memory of today's generations for his services among people having worked selflessly for the development and progress of the society.

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